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USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

This article considered the ways of effective use of information technologies in teaching young students. Based on the analysis of the regulatory legal framework, scientific and methodical literature on the studied topic, several effective methods of using modern computer technologies in education were classified.

Key words: *information technologies in education, students, computerization; electronic education, electronic system, special program, teachers, information technology, pedagogical technologies*

INTRODUCTION

On January 24, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev's Address to the Oliy Majlis outlined the following planned tasks for the further development of the higher education system: We need to clearly define the priority directions in the field of science for our country. No country can develop all fields of science at the same time. That is why we support the development of several priority areas of science every year. It is necessary to form an electronic platform of scientific achievements, a base of local and foreign scientific developments. Every higher education and research institution must establish cooperation with prestigious foreign universities and scientific centers. It is necessary to introduce information technologies that meet international standards at all stages of education. In order to train highly qualified specialists for the field, the "1 million programmers" project was implemented together with our foreign partners. The use of information technologies for higher goals includes several sub-goals, including increasing the convenience of learning, being able to use new opportunities, being aware of modern knowledge, distance learning, the possibility, as a convenience in improving qualifications including creating online programs. With the help of computer facilities, many opportunities can be created in the education system, and new researches and various initiatives are being recognized in this area.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Informatization of education is one of the most important conditions for the successful development of the processes of informatization of society. After all, in the field of education, people who not only shape the new information environment of the society, but also live and work in this new environment are trained and educated. Informatization of society is a set of interrelated political, socio-economic, scientific factors that provide each member of society with free access to any information sources, except for those that are legally confidential.

As a result of the effective introduction of information technologies into the educational process, a modern information environment is created in the management between the teacher and the student. Regarding the use of information technologies in the educational process, a single information system will be introduced, thus opening the way for the audience of students to receive the information they are looking for, the creation of such an information system in education is a pedagogical technology. Information technology is introduced to education in direct connection with certain educational and pedagogical principles: the principle of activity; the principle of the possibility of independent research; principle of educational work; principle of motivation; principle of theory and practical connection; These include the principle of increasing efficiency.

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Informatization of education is the process of providing the educational system with the theory and practice of developing and using new educational information technologies aimed at the implementation of educational and educational goals. It is customary to distinguish the following main directions of introduction of information technologies in education:

- 1) use of computer technologies as a teaching tool in educational processes, improvement of teaching-learning processes, improvement of its quality and efficiency;
- 2) use of computer technology as an educational tool
- 3) consideration of the possibilities of using computers and other modern information technology tools in education;
- 4) use of modern information technologies as a means of creative development of the student ;
- 5) use of computer technologies as a means of automation of control, testing and psychodiagnostic processes;
- 6) organization of communications based on the use of information technologies for the purpose of transfer and acquisition of pedagogical experience, methodological and educational literature ;
- 7) use of modern information technologies to organize intellectual recreation;
- 8) activation and improvement of the management of the educational institution and educational process based on the use of modern information technology systems;

Analysis of the current stage of development of information technologies, their use in education made it possible to identify conflicts between modern technical and software capabilities, global and local networks and the level of their use. Surveys of students show that with the help of information technology, it is possible to perform various tasks in the field of education. the ability to evaluate is a very easy and quick result for information technology, a method that can be effective, many people have problems in evaluating controls, complaining that the reason for this is not enough time set for the evaluation or, if not, there is no adequate approach of the evaluator. With the help of information technology, assessment can take place in various ways, it is done very quickly and accurately, but there are also those who insist that assessment without human intervention is sometimes not efficient enough. The fact that students and young people now effectively use computer systems to acquire new pedagogical knowledge allows them to save time and quickly learn new information.

increases the effectiveness of teaching students of pedagogical universities, if :

- if the models and programs that should be developed for young students are created on the basis of sufficient computer technologies;
- effective methods of using information technology tools have been developed;
- computers and modules are in compliance with the curriculum and processes;
- it should serve to develop the skills of scientific and research work, to increase professional and methodological training in the use of computer modularization systems and information exchange in the educational process for students;

The use of modern technologies helps to solve many problems in the educational system: pedagogical, organizational, economic and even theoretical and methodological fundamentals of the educational system are accompanied by fundamental changes. Thus, informatization of education leads to changes in certain aspects of the educational process.

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Today, along with the prospects in the development of information technologies, we need to take into account the shortcomings, and now it is necessary to follow a certain standard when receiving information.

The use of video methods with the help of information technologies in lessons is a very effective method, with the help of this method, various ideas and opinions can be expressed in a coherent sequence and delivered in an understandable language. It is necessary to use the test method as a sequence, correct answers to the questions on such a studied topic are carried out on the basis of a certain informational program, which provides the acquired knowledge in a timely manner provides an opportunity to repeat and test knowledge. The result of the method is quickly calculated with the help of information technology and the results are clearly visible to the student, such evaluation is considered an auxiliary method and does not affect the main grades, only the final test decides the final result.

With the help of modern information technology, it is possible to use such task and video method textbooks for independent research of students. Introduces the information, the student who did not get a high result or the desired result in the test will have to try to see this video method again.

In multimedia technologies, information is expressed in the form of images, sounds and actions, rather than in the form of text, in contrast to traditional technologies, it teaches students to be more active, attentive and curious in the lessons, because each piece of information recommended requires their participation and is done through movement. In the educational system, multimedia technologies are a tool that positively and effectively affects students by combining theoretical, practical, demonstrative, informative, training and control parts. In addition, the use of multimedia educational courses in the educational system allows to create high-quality video recordings of demonstrations of theoretical materials, virtual laboratory works and practices, simulated animation models of various processes, for this purpose students' educational classes, computer classes, teaching it is necessary to organize their practical activities in the technical equipment room, methodical rooms, and libraries.

It is very effective to share information to students through a centralized single system, algorithms that help to process and understand large amounts of information in a short period of time, these algorithms provide information in this field to the student who is looking for the information he needs. It can be delivered directly and sequentially in a program or module, of course, in this case, evaluation is considered a separate method of home instead.

We envisioned what great results we could achieve even through the video method, which only required control at the end. If we can introduce additional innovations on other methods, we can get good results in the education system.

CONCLUSION

One of the main didactic issues of this field - modeling of teaching and general methods of influencing visual objects occupy one of the important places in the creation of multimedia training courses for the educational system. In addition to specialized subjects, the student can get additional education, for example: learn programming languages, use online courses, simulators and communicate on any social network. You can get education regardless of your place of residence and age. Nowadays, the world wide web and different software products have different developments. Thanks to the development of information technologies, the idea of continuing distance education is fully realized. Also, information technology encourages more people to learn, to carry out various research projects, to create innovative projects and articles. In conclusion, the use of information

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technologies in the educational process is necessary to prepare teachers and students for modern life and work.

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